

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the present study is due to the increasing number of legal entities bankrupting against the background of economic instability and consequences of the pandemic. Financial insolvency of legal entities leads to job losses, reduced tax revenues, and deterioration of the social status of employees and their families.

Knowing the basics of economic insolvency allows entrepreneurs to manage risks better and to make more informed decisions. It helps minimize losses and find alternative sources of financing.

Literature Review

Crises in the global market significantly affect the bankruptcy rate of enterprises. Consumers often cut back on their spending during international crises, such as the 2008 financial crisis or the COVID-19 pandemic. This leads to decreased firm revenues, especially in sectors that depend on consumer demand, such as retail and services.

C. G. Stănescu writes that job losses and declining real incomes caused by the 2008 financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic affected consumers' ability to pay their debts. This led to high levels of non-performing loans (NPLs), affecting the stability of the financial industry and undermining economic recovery. The result was the need for faster debt collection and a sharp increase in unscrupulous informal debt collection practices (IDCPs) [1].

H. Nabilou writes that consolidation of different types of commercial and investment banking activities within a single entity, as well as interconnectedness of banking entities with other financial institutions, investment funds, and shadow banking system lay at the root of the global financial crisis. The author examines various measures to structurally separate banking entities and their core functions from riskier financial activities such as (proprietary) trading or investments in alternative investment funds [2].

R. Tkhasapso writes that crisis phenomena in the life of a company stimulate the need for accounting information to recreate the model of financial and economic activity of the organization in the pre-crisis period of its life cycle. Undoubtedly, risk of business interruption deforms the system of principles on which the organization's activity is based in normal functioning conditions, inevitably leading to transformation of accounting methods in bankrupt organizations. The author considers accounting principles in the context of enterprise insolvency and their impact on transforming bankrupt organizations' accounting and reporting system [3].

I. Kokorin describes the concept of group decision, which is associated with the insolvency of groups of enterprises that are operationally and financially interrelated. The author concludes that group resolution was not formed as a consistent and clearly defined legal principle but represents a variety of approaches, tools and practices that pursue different objectives [4].

F. R. Matenda et al. find that most studies on corporate bankruptcy detection focus on publicly traded firms in advanced economies. The authors review the literature on bankruptcy prediction of private firms in undeveloped economies [5].

According to B. Prusak, in countries characterized by an effective legal system and, at the same time, debtor-friendly bankruptcy legislation, the level of risk-taking among entrepreneurs is higher, which is reflected in a higher level of entrepreneurship and innovation [6].

The insolvency (bankruptcy) procedure is a complex process in which information and mathematical methods play a key role. They are applied at the stages of data collection, financial condition assessment, scenario modeling, process optimization, and decision-making.

Standard methods of manipulation are overstatement or understatement of revenues and/or expenses. According to E. Siverin and D. Veganzones, information about earnings management, including potential earnings manipulations detected in financial statements, will improve the accuracy of bankruptcy prediction models [7].

A. Rafal discusses further ways of developing legislation on insolvency (bankruptcy). According to the author, development of digital technologies significantly impacts optimization of insolvency (bankruptcy) proceedings [8].

G. Loiacono and E. Rulli discuss application of innovative technologies SupTech and RegTech for crisis resolution. SupTech (Supervisory Technology) are technologies used by regulators to improve the efficiency of control and supervision over the activities of financial market participants. RegTech (Regulatory Technology) are technologies used to make it easier for financial organizations to comply with regulatory requirements. The authors argue that insolvency resolution technologies can help determine the optimal liquidation strategy for small and medium-sized financial companies [9].

H. Kim et al. use neural network algorithms to improve bankruptcy prediction efficiency compared to other classification methods such as logistic regression et al. [10].

I. Abid also uses neural network techniques to select variables and predict business bankruptcy. The authors show that profitability, solvency, taxation, and the importance of investment have strong explanatory power in predicting bankruptcy [11].

Thus, the scientific problem of economic insolvency of legal entities in the business environment is primarily related to the company's inability to fulfill its financial obligations. Private questions arise about how to accurately define insolvency criteria, what metrics and ratios to use, and at what stage bankruptcy proceedings should be initiated.

Insolvency of legal entities can lead to increased unemployment, loss of investor confidence, and reduced competitiveness in the market. The scientific problem is the need to study these effects and find ways to minimize them.

There is insufficient coverage of the various legal rules and procedures governing bankruptcy for small and medium-sized enterprises, as well as the possibilities of improving the existing legislative initiatives.

The article aims to analyze signs of economic insolvency of legal entities in the entrepreneurial environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used were articles from peer-reviewed periodicals: Journal of Consumer Policy, European Business Organization Law Review, Management Review Quarterly, International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal, Annals of Operations Research, Journal of Banking Regulation, Computational Economics, European Business Organization Law Review and others.

The authors monitored regulatory and legal documentation on bankruptcy and financial crises.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The Federal Law of the Russian Federation under insolvency (bankruptcy) understands the inability of the debtor to satisfy creditors' claims on monetary circumstances fully, on payment of severance payments, and (or) on payment of wages to persons working or who worked under an employment contract, and (or) to fulfill the obligation to pay mandatory payments recognized by the arbitration court or occurred as a result of completion of extrajudicial bankruptcy procedure of a citizen [16].

Impossibility for an insolvent legal entity to continue activity is manifested in the fact that it cannot restore solvency, and it cannot typically conduct financial and economic activity. Inexpediency the legal entity to continue activity is concluded in the fact that the socio-economic significance of such activity, economic and production potential, attractiveness for investors, and competitiveness of the output products are absent.

Signs of bankruptcy of a legal entity are reflected in Art. 3 of the Federal Law of 26.10.2002 No. 127-FZ 'On Insolvency (bankruptcy)' [Ibid]. [Ibid]. By the said article, a legal entity must have arrears of:

- monetary obligations to its partners;
- wages and severance pay to its employees;
- compulsory payments (taxes, fees).

An important point is the indication that the formed debt is not repaid within 3 months from the moment when such obligations should have been fulfilled.

Clause 2 of Article 6 of the Federal Law of 26.10.2002 No. 127-FZ 'On Insolvency (bankruptcy)' enshrines the norm that the arbitration court initiates insolvency proceedings when the total amount of debt of a legal entity is not less than 300,000 RUR.

Thus, the general signs of insolvency of a legal entity are a debt of 300,000 RUR and non-payment of such debt by the legal entity for at least 3 months from when it arose.

These signs give the right to apply to court with a petition for the recognition of a legal entity as bankrupt to the following persons:

- employees who have not been paid wages or benefits;
- authorized bodies if 30 days have passed since the decision on debt collection;
- creditors of the legal entity if there are claims satisfied by a court decision that has entered into legal force [17].

A legal entity also has the right to apply to court in case it foresees its insolvency, and there are circumstances indicating that it will not be able to fulfill its monetary obligations in time, which is specified in Art. 8 of the Federal Law of the Federal Law of 26.10.2002 No. 127-FZ 'On Insolvency (bankruptcy)' [16].

Paragraph 1 of Art. 9 of the said Law contains cases when the head of a legal entity is obliged to file a bankruptcy petition with the court:

- repayment of debts incurred to one or more creditors will lead to the fact that the fulfillment of other obligations will be impossible;
- the authorized body of the legal entity has decided to file a relevant application with the court;
- foreclosure on the property of the legal entity will make it impossible to continue its activities or complicate such activities;
- the legal entity has a 3-month overdue debt on wages and benefits to its employees, which was formed due to insufficient funds.

Paragraphs 5, 6 of Article 177 of the Law under consideration contain unique signs of bankruptcy of agricultural organizations:

- total debt should be not less than 500,000 RUR;

- non-fulfillment of claims on debt repayment within 3 months from the moment they should have been fulfilled.

As we see, the amount of claims for recognizing an agricultural organization as bankrupt is 200,000 RUR higher than the general rule.

By Paragraphs 1, 2 of Art. 177 of the Federal Law of 26.10.2002 No. 127-FZ 'On Insolvency (Bankruptcy)', the following legal entities are classified as agricultural organizations:

- agricultural producers whose main activities are production and (or) processing of agricultural goods;
- at that, the proceeds from the sale of such goods are to be not less than half of the total proceeds of such enterprise;
- fishing artels whose activities are related to production and (or) processing of agricultural goods and catch of aquatic biological resources; proceeds from the sale of such goods should be at least 70% of the total proceeds of the enterprise [Ibid].

Concerning a credit organization, signs of bankruptcy are outlined in Paragraph 1 of Article 189.8 of the Law:

- Organization is unable to satisfy the claims of its employees and partners for the payment of funds; to fulfill the obligation to pay taxes and fees, both its own and at the behest of its clients from their bank accounts;
- Failure to fulfill these obligations within 14 days from the date when they should have been fulfilled;
- The assets of the credit organization are insufficient to fulfill the obligations.

Thus, the general signs of insolvency of a legal entity are debts to employees and partners, budgets of various levels for 300,000 RUR, and non-payment within 3 months from the date of such occurrence. The legislator distinguishes two types of insolvency (bankruptcy) criteria – insolvency and non-payment.

Insolvency and non-payment are important signs of insolvency (bankruptcy) for legal entities.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Study of economic insolvency of legal entities opens wide prospects for both research activities and practical realization. One of the directions is development of more effective mechanisms for predicting bankruptcy. For this purpose, modern methods of data analysis (neural networks, artificial intelligence, etc.) are required. It is crucial to identify key financial and non-financial indicators, based on which it is possible to detect signs of bankruptcy in advance.

It is necessary to improve existing bankruptcy procedures and develop new approaches that will be more effective and less costly for all parties involved in the process.

Practical recommendations for companies on effective risk management and financial planning need to be developed. Organizations need an in-depth understanding of causes of bankruptcy, both financial and non-financial, i.e. management practices and external factors affecting business sustainability.

Studying the impact of economic insolvency on unemployment and social well-being is necessary. It is relevant to develop programs to support laid-off workers and help them retrain.

Thus, study of economic insolvency of legal entities is not only of high scientific value but also of practical importance for business, government and society as a whole. It can help create a more sustainable business environment that promotes economic growth and development.

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